

SOME ALIPHATIC MONOCARBOXYLATE COMPLEXES OF DIVALENT METALS IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION. PART VII. MANGANESE ACETATO COMPLEXES

BY S. K. SIDDHANTA AND S. N. BANERJEE

The p_H values of aqueous solution mixtures of manganese acetate and hydrochloric acid at different concentrations, after attainment of equilibrium, have been determined and the data obtained have been utilised to calculate the mass action constants, k_1 and k_2 , for the two successive equilibria $MnAc_2 \rightleftharpoons MnAc^+ + Ac^-$ and $MnAc^+ \rightleftharpoons Mn^{2+} + Ac^-$, applying Bjerrum's method. The inapplicability of the method (modification of Bjerrum's method) of Siddhanta and Banerjee (Part III, this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 323) has been accounted for and a method has been suggested to calculate the values of thermodynamic dissociation constants, K_1 and K_2 , from the values of the mass action constants determined above, by the direct application of "law of mass action", taking into account the activity coefficients of the individual ion, calculated from the ionic strength of the above solution mixture, employing the "Debye-Hückel limiting law".

Manganese acetate dissociates in aqueous solution in two stages :

In the present paper the thermodynamic equilibrium constants, ' K_1 ' and ' K_2 ' (vide equations 1 and 2), have been found out from the determination of p_H of the solution mixtures of manganese acetate and hydrochloric acid by following a similar (but not identical) procedure as adopted in Parts III and V of this series (this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 323, 343).

$$K_1 = \frac{a_{MnAc^+} \cdot a_{Ac^-}}{a_{MnAc_2}} = k_1 \cdot \frac{f_{MnAc^+} \cdot f_{Ac^-}}{f_{MnAc_2}} \quad \dots (1)$$

and
$$K_2 = \frac{a_{Mn^{2+}} \cdot a_{Ac^-}}{a_{MnAc^+}} = k_2 \cdot \frac{f_{Mn^{2+}} \cdot f_{Ac^-}}{f_{MnAc^+}} \quad \dots (2)$$

where ' k_1 ' and ' k_2 ' are the classical concentration constants given by

$$k_1 = \frac{CMnAc^+ \cdot CAc^-}{CMnAc_2} \quad \text{and} \quad \dots (3)$$

$$k_2 = \frac{CMn^{2+} \cdot CAc^-}{CMnAc^+} \quad \dots (4)$$

The values of ' k_1 ' and ' k_2 ' were found out by the graphical solution of the equation (5b), given in Part III (*loc. cit.*) as in the case of lead acetate complex. These values of ' k_1 ' and ' k_2 ' were utilised to find out the ionic strength, ' μ ', and the activity coefficients, ' f_1 ' and ' f_2 ', for monovalent and divalent ions respectively, the procedure being identical as that adopted for lead acetate, referred to above.

Unfortunately, in the case of manganese acetate, comparatively high concentration of the salt had to be used for the sake of accuracy in calculating ' $a_{M^{2+}}$ ' from p_H values. As a result of using higher concentrations of manganese acetate, as also of its greater dissociation, the ionic strengths of the mixtures used rose high, and in the regions where ' μ ' was somewhat lower, recalculated value of ' x ' approached ' $2C$ ' quite closely, so that ' $2C-x$ ' was erroneous. In the cases of lead acetate and lead propionate (Part III, *loc. cit.*) and cobalt acetate (Part V, *loc. cit.*), however, solution mixtures with values of ' μ ' less than 0.05 in most cases could be used without prejudice to the value of ' $a_{M^{2+}}$ ' in spite of the experimental error in the p_H determinations. Since the ionic strength was low, the value of ' f_1 ' obtained was reasonably accurate and the value of ' x ' calculated, using this value of ' f_1 ', contained relatively small error and, hence, the relative error in " $2C-x$ " was also small. Moreover, the dissociation was such that " $2C-x$ " was substantially greater than zero for the solution mixtures used. Manganese acetate, however, has a much larger degree of dissociation, leading naturally to a small value of " $2C-x$ ", and if " $2C-x$ " is determined by the procedure followed for lead acetate, it will contain larger relative error arising from the inaccuracy of the value of ' f_1 ' used. Therefore in the case of manganese acetate, the functions

$$c_{Ac^-} = \frac{x}{2C-x} \cdot f_1^2 f_2 \quad \text{and} \quad c_{Ac^-} = \frac{C-x}{2C-x} \cdot f_2$$

could not be calculated with sufficient accuracy, and as such the graphical solution of equation (5C) (Part III, *loc. cit.*) was not possible in this case.

The constants K_1 and K_2 were, however, determined by the direct application of equations (1) and (2) in the forms (1a) and (2a) respectively.

$$K_1 = \frac{c_{MnAc^+} \cdot c_{Ac^-}}{c_{MnAc_2}} \cdot f_1^2 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1a)$$

(f_{MnAc_2} being equal to 1, since, $MnAc_2$ is a non-electrolyte) and

$$K_2 = \frac{c_{Mn^{2+}} \cdot c_{Ac^-}}{c_{MnAc^+}} \cdot f_2 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2a)$$

In these calculations the values of ' $c_{Mn^{2+}}$ ', ' c_{MnAc^+} ', ' f_1 ' and ' f_2 ' already found, as indicated above from the approximate value of k_2 ($k_2 = 50 \times 10^{-3}$), have been used*; c_{MnAc_2} has been calculated from equation (5).

$$C = c_{MnAc_2} + c_{MnAc^+} + c_{Mn^{2+}} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

This value, however, involves errors in both ' $c_{Mn^{2+}}$ ' and ' c_{MnAc^+} ' and, hence, is not so accurate; the relative error in ' c_{MnAc_2} ' becomes larger and larger as " $c_{Mn^{2+}} + c_{MnAc^+}$ " approaches ' C '. For this reason, the values of ' K_1 ' obtained are not at all accurate and are only indicative of the order. By averaging all the values of ' K_1 ', obtained in the above way, we get $K_1 = 1.43 \times 10^{-1}$ at room temperature. The individual values of ' K_1 ' are erratic, apparently showing no dependence on ionic strengths for the respective solution mixtures.

* Values of ' c_{Ac^-} ', recalculated by the equation $c_{Ac^-} = \frac{K_2 C_2}{a_{M^{2+}} f_1}$ have been used.

The values of ' K_2 ' obtained, however, become progressively lower at higher ionic strength, showing the dependence of ' K_2 ', so calculated, on the respective ionic strengths, evidently due to the inapplicability of the "Debye Hückel limiting law" to solutions of finite ionic strength, as has already been explained in detail in the case of lead acetate (this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 269). The pK_2 values corresponding to those of ' K_2 ', obtained in this paper, are plotted against the respective values of $\sqrt{\mu}$ in the graph, obtained for manganese chloride and acetic acid mixtures, shown in Fig. 2 in Part VI (*ibid.*, 1958, 35, 349), and these points (represented by $\square$ mark) have been found to lie on the same straight line curve representing $pK/\sqrt{\mu}$ plot of the above paper. The value of the thermodynamic constant ' K_2 ' is therefore the same as that obtained in Part VI (*loc. cit.*), and it is $K_2 = 60.3 \times 10^{-3}$ at room temperature.

There appears to be no previous work on the determination of these constants in the case of manganese acetate.

TABLE I

The symbols used in the table headings and their evaluations are same as in Part III (*loc. cit.*).

Soln. No.	C*	C ₀ *	t°	f_{H^+}	$\frac{a_A}{(K_2 = 1.80 \times 10^{-3})} \times 10^3$	$a_A^{-1} \cdot \frac{C-x}{2C-x} \times 10^3$	$a_A^{-2} \cdot \frac{x}{2C-x} \times 10^3$
1	0.025	0.020	28.5°	4.758	20.62	-34.48	1.84
2	0.035	"	"	4.955	32.46	-32.39	3.16
3	0.040	"	"	5.01	39.47	-37.43	4.51
4	0.045	"	"	5.07	42.31	-26.34	4.02
5	0.050	"	"	5.12	47.43	-25.38	4.66
6	0.055	"	"	5.16	52.02	-23.30	5.13
7	0.060	"	"	5.21	58.35	-25.71	6.40
8	0.065	"	"	5.24	62.61	-23.25	6.83
9	0.070	"	"	5.25	64.06	-16.10	6.17
10	0.075	"	"	5.29	70.13	-17.83	7.42
11	0.080	"	"	5.31	73.47	-14.88	7.58
12	0.099	"	25.3°	5.40	90.44	-11.77	10.31
13	0.108	"	"	5.42	64.74	-6.31	10.16
14	0.117	"	28.8°	5.46	103.80	-5.70	12.10
15	0.126	"	25.3°	5.47	106.20	-0.17	11.31
16	0.135	"	"	5.49	111.10	+3.12	11.65
17	0.050	0.010	33.0°	5.49	55.55	-25.07	5.87
18	0.100	"	"	5.72	94.24	-4.17	9.66
19	0.200	"	"	5.93	152.54	+24.06	15.92
20	0.250	"	"	5.99	174.75	+36.16	17.89
21	0.050	0.050	28.5°	4.497	28.30	-36.77	2.88
22	"	0.045	"	4.587	31.30	-34.73	3.15
23	"	0.040	"	4.682	34.61	-33.56	3.52
24	"	0.035	"	4.786	38.49	-34.14	4.11
25	"	0.030	"	4.887	41.45	-31.12	4.30
26	"	0.025	"	4.991	44.07	-27.17	4.34
27	"	0.020	"	5.130	48.59	-28.78	5.16
28	"	0.015	"	5.270	50.28	-22.23	4.75
29	"	0.010	"	5.480	54.39	-21.99	5.35

* 'C' and 'C₀' denote respectively the molar conc. of MnAc₂ and HCl.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Manganese acetate (Thomas Tyler and Co., London) was purified by crystallising twice from acetic acid. The residue was then washed with ice-cold water and finally with ether. $Mn(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ (Cadenhead and Vinning, *Can. Chem. Met.*, 1924, 8, 64) requires Mn, 22.42% (found as sulphate : 22.50%).

Stock solutions of manganese acetate and hydrochloric acid were prepared. In these solutions manganese was estimated gravimetrically as sulphate and the strength of the acid solutions, by titration with a standard alkali. For preparation of solution mixtures, such volumes of manganese acetate and hydrochloric acid solutions were measured out that on dilution to 10 c.c., the desired initial concentrations 'C' and 'C₀' for manganese acetate and hydrochloric acid respectively were attained. After keeping the mixtures in a closed room for about three hours to reach equilibrium, the p_H values were determined by following the same procedure and observing the same precautions as described in Part II (*ibid.*, 1958, 35, 279).

TABLE II

Soln. No. (as in Table I).	$\dagger C_{MnAc} \times 10^3$.	$\dagger C_{Mn} \times 10^3$.	$C_{MnAc} \times 10^3$. (Eq. 5).	μ (Part III, Eq. 10).	$C_{Ac} \times 10^3$ (Part III, Eq. 8b). $K_a = 1.75 \times 10^{-5}$.	$K_1 \times 10^1$ (Eq. 1a).	$K_2 \times 10^2$ (Eq. 2a).
1	6.94	16.84	1.22	0.05746	26.5	0.859 †	2.095
2	12.86	19.80	2.34	0.07226	43.3	1.266	1.866*
3	16.83	21.32	1.85	0.08079	53.6	2.500†	1.785
4	18.53	21.89	4.58	0.08420	60.3	1.234	1.822
5	21.69	22.87	5.44	0.09030	65.7	1.293	1.688*
6	24.64	23.69	6.67	0.09571	72.7	1.298	1.633
7	28.87	24.74	6.39	0.10309	82.7	1.758	1.569*
8	31.80	25.40	7.80	0.10820	89.5	1.686	1.526
9	32.82	25.62	11.50	0.10968	91.9	1.199	1.514
10	37.15	26.49	11.36	0.11562	102.0	1.495	1.461*
11	49.59	26.94	13.47	0.12041	107.4	1.397	1.432
12	52.45	28.99	17.56	0.13942	136.2	1.690	1.303*
13	55.82	29.46	22.72	0.14420	144.0	1.449	1.276
14	63.05	30.37	23.58	0.15416	159.8	1.698	1.216
15	64.89	30.55	30.56	0.15669	164.3	1.377	1.204
16	68.91	31.04	35.05	0.16208	173.3	1.322	1.176*
17	23.40	21.07	5.53	0.08661	76.41	1.620	1.726
18	50.57	26.83	22.60	0.13106	140.00	1.336	1.151*
19	98.17	32.18	69.65	0.19471	250.00	1.250	1.050*
20	117.50	33.62	98.88	0.21836	291.66	1.157	0.924*
21	17.27	30.51	2.22	0.10880	40.5	1.452	1.519†
22	18.10	29.05	2.76	0.10534	44.6	1.371	1.550
23	19.28	27.71	3.11	0.10231	49.0	1.425	1.575
24	20.42	26.53	3.55	0.10001	54.3	1.729	1.597
25	20.54	25.25	3.81	0.09669	58.1	1.538	1.606*
26	21.13	23.97	4.90	0.09304	61.4	1.293	1.661
27	22.43	23.08	4.49	0.09167	67.4	1.654	1.672
28	21.84	21.72	6.44	0.08700	69.1	1.172	1.718
29	22.68	20.85	6.47	0.08523	74.5	1.316	1.737†

† Solving equations (4) and (9a) of Part III (*loc.cit.*) with a_{Ac^-} from Table I, these are calculated.

* These values have only been plotted on $pK/\sqrt{\mu}$ curve in Fig. 2 of Part VI (*loc.cit.*) where the points have been shown by □ mark. The values of 'K₁' without asterisks, if similarly plotted, also fall on the same straight line, but this has not been done to avoid clumsiness in the figure.

† These values were not considered while taking mean (vide: theoretical).

Table I shows the experimental p_B values and the corresponding values of the functions:

$$a_{A^-} \cdot \frac{C-x}{2C-x} \times 10^3 \text{ and } a_{A^-} \cdot \frac{x}{2C-x} \times 10^3$$

where A^- represents acetate ion and 'x', total concentration of "free acetic acid species"

FIG. 1

(Ordinate magnified 10 times of the abscissa).

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given by $c_{A^-} + C_a$). Fig. 1 represents equation (5b) (vide Part III, *loc. cit.*) graphically (using " $c_{A^-} = a_{A^-}$ " in 5b for solutions of low ionic strengths). The slope and intercept on the ordinate of this straight line curve give the values of k_1 and k_2 as $k_1 = 210.0 \times 10^{-3}$ and $k_2 = 50.0 \times 10^{-3}$. These may be regarded as the average values of ' k_1 ' and ' k_2 ' over the range of ionic strengths employed. In Fig. 1 the circles represent data from Table I for the first 20 solution mixtures (Nos. 1 to 20) in which ' C_a ' is constant and ' C ' varying, and the triangles represent those for the last 9 solution mixtures (Nos. 20 to 29) in which ' C ' is constant and ' C_a ' varies. Table II, in which the values of ' K_1 ' and ' K_2 ' calculated by following the procedure already described, is self-explanatory.

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SOME ALIPHATIC MONOCARBOXYLATE COMPLEXES OF BIVALENT METALS IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION. PART VIII. NICKEL MONO-ACETATO COMPLEX

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The composition of the complex formed between Ni^{2+} and acetate ions has been found to be $NiAc^+$, from a study of the equilibrium H^+ -concentrations in mixtures of equimolecular nickel nitrate and acetic acid solutions, with the help of "Job's method of continued variation", employing the increase of H^+ -concentration as a new index property.

The thermodynamic dissociation constant, K , for the equilibrium $NiAc^+ \rightleftharpoons Ni^{2+} + Ac^-$ has been found out as 75.9×10^{-3} at $21.3-22.0^\circ$, as in Part I of this series.

The same procedure as adopted in Part I (this *Journal*, 1958, 38, 269) was followed to determine the thermodynamic dissociation constant for the equilibrium,

(where Ac^- represents acetate ion)

$$K = \frac{a_{\text{Ni}^{2+}} \cdot a_{\text{Ac}^-}}{a_{\text{NiAc}^+}} = \frac{c_{\text{Ni}^{2+}} \cdot c_{\text{Ac}^-}}{c_{\text{NiAc}^+}} \cdot \frac{f_{\text{Ni}^{2+}} \cdot f_{\text{Ac}^-}}{f_{\text{NiAc}^+}}, \quad \dots (1)$$

from a study of the p_H of solution mixtures containing '1-x' volume of nickel nitrate and 'x' volume of acetic acid, 'x' varying from 0.1 to 0.9, and both parent solutions being at the same concentration, 'C'. The composition of the complex formed has been determined, as in the case of lead acetate (Part I, *loc. cit.*). From Y-x plots it has been observed that the maximum value of 'Y' corresponds to the reacting proportion 1:1 for nickel nitrate and acetic acid. It is evident therefore that under the condition of the experiment, the following equilibrium alone is most predominant, and the formation of higher complexes, e.g., NiAc_2 , NiAc_3 , etc., is negligible. The reaction thus becomes

EXPERIMENTAL

Nickel nitrate and acetic acid were of A.R. quality. All solutions were prepared with conductivity water. Stock solutions of nickel nitrate and acetic acid were prepared, and in these solutions nickel was determined with dimethylglyoxime and acetic acid, by titration with a standard alkali solution. After keeping the mixtures in a closed room for 4 hours, the p_H values were determined by following the same procedure and observing the same precautions as were done in Part II (*ibid.*, 58, 38, 279).

FIG. 1

TABLE I
(HAc represents acetic acid)

1-x.	Solution mixtures in c.c.			Concentration of parent solutions.			
	HAc.	Ni(NO ₃) ₂ .	H ₂ O.	M/5; C=0.2; $\rho=1$; temp.=21.3°.	Increase in [H ⁺] (Y × 10 ⁴).	M/10; C=0.1; $\rho=1$; temp.=22°.	Increase in [H ⁺] (Y' × 10 ⁴).
				ρ_{H^+}		ρ_{H^+}	
	9	1	...	2.690	5.42	2.882	0.70
0.1	9	...	1	2.824		*(12.42)	
	8	2	...	2.673	6.44	2.882	1.36
0.2	8	...	2	2.830		(11.76)	
	7	3	...	2.673	7.17	2.887	1.91
0.3	7	...	3	2.852		(11.06)	
	6	4	...	2.673	8.32	2.897	2.54
0.4	6	...	4	2.889		(10.14)	
	5	5	...	2.690	8.40	2.928	2.55
0.5	5	...	5	2.920		(9.25)	
	4	6	...	2.724	8.32	2.964	2.62
0.6	4	...	6	2.980		(8.24)	
	3	7	...	2.767	7.98	3.007	2.66
0.7	3	...	7	3.040		(7.18)	
	2	8	...	2.830	7.51	3.079	2.54
0.8	2	...	8	3.138		(5.80)	
	1	9	...	2.957	6.11	3.226	1.84
0.9	1	...	9	3.307		(4.10)	

N. B. In the present case the hydrogen-ion concentration of the mixture of '1-x' c.c. of nickel nitrate solution at concentrations C=0.2 and C=0.1 with 'x' c.c. of water is very small and has therefore been neglected in calculating the value of 'Y'.

* In this case with C=0.1, the [H⁺] ($\approx a_{H^+} \times 10^4$) for the acetic acid solutions are calculated from the relations,

$$K_a = \frac{Ca^2}{1-a} \quad \text{and} \quad [H^+] = aC,$$

where a is the degree of dissociation of acetic acid; C is the concentration of acetic acid and K_a , the ionisation constant of acetic acid at 22° (1.75×10^{-5} from "Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solutions" by Harned and Owen, 2nd. ed., p. 580). These values are shown in parentheses.

TABLE II

The symbols used in the table headings and their evaluations are same as in Part I (*loc. cit.*).

1-x.	Solution mixtures in c.c.			Concentration of parent solutions.			
	HAc.	Ni(NO ₃) ₂ .		M/5; C=0.2; $\rho=1$; temp.=21.3°.	M/10; C=0.1; $\rho=1$; temp.=22°.		
				μ .	$K \times 10^3$.	μ .	$K \times 10^3$.
0.1	9	1		0.0610	17.56	0.0310	35.76
0.2	8	2		0.1205	11.80	0.0607	23.69
0.3	7	3		0.1801	8.96	0.0903	16.83
0.4	6	4		0.2398	6.42	0.1203	13.11
0.5	5	5		0.2996	5.05	0.1503	12.07
0.6	4	6		0.3596	4.27	0.1802	10.47
0.7	3	7		0.4195	3.33	0.2100	8.37
0.8	2	8		0.4794	2.53	0.2399	6.91
0.9	1	9		0.5395	1.87	0.2699	6.09

N. B. Taken ionisation constant of acetic acid to be 1.75×10^{-5} (Harned and Owen, *loc. cit.*).

The results of p_H determinations for mixtures of two sets of equimolar parent solutions of nickel nitrate and acetic acid, one having concentration $C=0.2$ and another set $C=0.1$, have been shown in Table I.

FIG. 2

(The sign $\square$ represents the plot of pK_2/μ from Table II of part IX).

The values of 'Y' against the corresponding values of 'x' from Table I, for mixtures of nickel nitrate and acetic acid solutions, both being at concentration $C=0.2M$, have been graphically represented by curve I, and those for both parent solutions at concentration $C=0.1M$, by curve II, in Fig. 1. The values of ' μ ' and ' K ' for the solution mixtures, studied in the present work, have been obtained by following the same procedure as described in Part I (*loc. cit.*) and these are shown in Table II. As in the previous case (vide Part I), the plot of ' K ' against ' μ ' from Table II yields a smooth curve, which has not been used to evaluate the value of ' K ' by extrapolation to zero ionic strength. In Fig. 2, the graph $pK (= -\log K)$ against $\sqrt{\mu}$ from Table II gives a straight line curve which on extrapolation to $\sqrt{\mu}=0$ gives the value of pK corresponding to the true thermodynamic constant, K . These values of ' pK ' and ' K ' at $\sqrt{\mu}=0$ are 1.12 and 75.9×10^{-3} at $21.3-22^\circ$ respectively.

Critical comments on the previous work on the subject, as also on the present work have been made in Part IX of this series.

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